

Prospective Clinico-Pathological Assessment of Different Types of Neoplastic and Non-Neoplastic Lesions of the Ovary

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Abstract

Aim: To analyse the frequency of ovarian (20%) cases was malignant. In benign ovarian neoplasm, most lesions their clinico-histological features in a rural set up.

Material & Methods: A prospective clinico-pathological study of 120 cases of non-neoplastic and neoplastic lesions of ovary was conducted in Department of Pathology, Patna Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India over the period of one year. The materials for this study, ovarian specimen was obtained from hysterectomy specimen with unilateral or bilateral adnexa, and oophorectomy and/or cystectomy specimens received in the department.

Results: Amongst 120 cases studied during study period, 60 were nonneoplastic and remaining 60 were neoplastic. The most common non-neoplastic lesion found was solitary follicular cysts (65%) followed by corpus luteal cysts (28.3%) Incidence of malignancy is inversely proportional to parity. In the present study, it was observed that malignant tumor were common in nulliparous women.

Conclusion: Ovarian lesion possess wide gamut of histology. Specific diagnoses are made on routine gross and histological examination.

Keywords: Benign, Malignant, Ovary, Ovarian cyst, Tumors

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Introduction

The ovary has three main histologic compartments i.e. the surface Mullerian epithelium, the germ cells and the sex-cord stromal cells. Each compartment gives rise to distinct non-neoplastic and neoplastic lesions [1,2]. Such lesions can be found from neonatal to postmenopausal ages and it accounts for around 30% of all female genital Cancers [3]. The incidence and prevalence of ovarian cancer vary in different geographical areas of the country. Indian trend analysis reveals a steady increase in the age standardized incidence rate of ovarian cancer ranging from 0.26%

to 2.44% per year in different area registries [4].

Ovary is an important organ as it is concerned with the production of progeny. The ovary consists of sex cells and mesenchymal cells which are totipotential and multipotential respectively. So, whenever it develops neoplasia, almost any types of tumor can result. [5]

Among the cancers of female genital tract, the incidence of ovarian tumor ranks below only carcinoma of cervix. [6] It represent about 30% of all cancers of the female genital system and 4% of all cancers in

women. [3] Indian trend analysis reveal a steady increase in the age-standardized incidence rate of ovarian cancer, comprising up to 8.7% of cancers in different parts of the country. [7]

Early diagnosis is difficult due to its asymptomatic nature, inaccessible site and the limited use of various new techniques like cytology and biopsy. Thus, ovarian neoplasm offers a good field for research [8]. Thus, this study aims to analyses the frequency of ovarian (20%) cases were malignant. In benign ovarian neoplasm, most lesions their clinico-histological features in a rural set up.

Material & Methods:

A prospective clinico-pathological study of 120 cases of non-neoplastic and neoplastic lesions of ovary was conducted in Department of Pathology, Patna Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India over the period of one year. The materials for this study, ovarian specimen was obtained from hysterectomy specimen with unilateral or bilateral adnexa, and oophorectomy and/or cystectomy specimens received in the department.

Relevant clinical information regarding the age, clinical features, radiological findings and provisional diagnosis were obtained. The specimens were analyzed in detail macroscopically for various parameters like size, external surface, and consistency and cut sections with contents of cyst.

The tissues were processed by routine paraffin techniques and sections stained with Haematoxylin and Eosin were taken for microscopic examination.

The non-neoplastic and neoplastic lesions from representative sections were studied and classified according to World Health Organization (WHO) classification 2002 and staging is done according to International Federation of Gynecology and Obstetrics (FIGO) staging.

Results:

Amongst 120 cases studied during study period, 60 were nonneoplastic and remaining 60 were neoplastic. The most common non-neoplastic lesion found was solitary follicular cysts (65%) followed by corpus luteal cysts (28.3%) [Table 1].

Table 1: Showing frequency of non-neoplastic lesions of ovary

Non-neoplastic lesions of ovary	Number of cases	Percentage
Follicular cyst	39	65%
Corpus luteal cyst	17	28.3%
Inclusion cyst	01	1.67%
Endometriosis	03	5%
Total	60	100%
Mean	26.22	30.31

In current study most of the patients of non-neoplastic lesions presented with more than one symptom [Table 2].

Table 2: Showing the clinical symptoms of 75 cases of non-neoplastic lesions of ovary

Clinical symptoms	no. of cases	Percentage
Pain in abdomen	12	20%
Menstrual irregularities/abnormal vaginal bleeding	26	43.3%
Pain in abdomen with white discharge per vagina.	8	13.3%
Pain in abdomen with mass per abdomen	5	8.33%
Mass per abdomen only.	7	11.7%
Pain in abdomen with Menstrual irregularities/ abnormal vaginal bleeding	2	3.33%
Total	60	100%

Most common symptom was menstrual irregularities/abnormal vaginal bleeding present in 26 (43.3%) patients

Among the 60 neoplastic ovarian lesions 45 cases were benign and 15 cases were malignant [Table 3].

Table 3: Showing frequency of ovarian neoplasm

Nature of tumors	Number of cases	Percentage
I. Epithelial stromal tumors		
A. Serous tumors		
1. Serous cystadenoma	21	35%
2. Serous papillary cystadenoma	3	5%
3. Borderline serous tumor	1	1.67%
4. Serous cyst adenocarcinoma	3	5%
B. Mucinous tumors		
1. Mucinous cystadenoma	5	8.33%
2. Mucinous papillary cystadenoma	1	1.67%
3. Mucinous cyst adenocarcinoma	2	3.33%
C. endometrioid tumor-Adenocarcinoma type	1	1.67%
II. Germ cell tumors		
1. Benign cystic teratoma	13	21.7%
2. Dysgerminoma	2	3.33%
3. Struma ovarii	1	1.67%
III. Sex cord stromal tumors		
1. Granulosa cell tumor	1	1.67%
2. Fibroma	3	5%
IV. Metastatic		
1. Metastatic tumor.	4	6.67%
Total	60	100%

Incidence of malignancy is inversely proportional to parity. In the present study, it was observed that malignant tumor were common in nulliparous women [Table 4].

Table 4 Showing incidence of marital status and parity distribution

Marital status and parity	Type of tumor		Total
	Benign	Malignant	
Unmarried	4	--	4
Nulliparous	7	6	13
Parity 1	3	2	5
Parity 2	15	1	16
Parity 3	10	2	12
Parity 4	3	3	6
Parity 5 and above	3	1	4
Total	45	15	60

Figure 1:

Figure 1: Follicular cyst: benign cells with round nuclei and scanty cytoplasm against a bloody background (Pap ×200)

Figure 2:

Figure 2: sheets of benign epithelial cells with uniform nuclei and cytoplasmic vacuolation (Pap ×400)

Figure 1:**Figure 2:**

Figure 3: Benign cystic teratoma; benign squamous cells against a dirty background of keratinous debris (Pap $\times 400$)

Figure 4: Granulosa cell tumor; monomorphic cells and nuclei with finely granular chromatin (Pap $\times 200$)

Discussion:

Studies done by Pilli et al [9] and Gupta et al. [10] They have reported figures of 75.2%, 2.8%, 21.9% and 72.9%, 4.10%, 22.9% for benign, borderline and malignant ovarian tumors respectively. Scully et al [3] also observed that benign tumors were more common than malignant tumors, incidence being 75-80% of all ovarian neoplasm. However, Manker and Jain [11] and Ahmed et al [12] in their studies observed a relative decrease in the percentage of benign tumors and consequent increase in the percentage of malignant tumors. According to Mankar and Jain 63.04% tumors were benign, 5.84% were borderline and 31.12% were malignant. Ahmad et al., who reported an incidence of 59.18%, 0.2% and 40.81% for benign, borderline and malignant tumors respectively.

In addition, various studies performed by different researchers offered similar observations regarding the incidences of malignant and benign tumors. [13-15] The U.S. National Institutes of Health estimates that 5%–10% of women in the United States undergo surgical exploration for and ovarian cyst in their lifetimes and that 13%–21% of these cysts will be malignant. [16] Ovarian cancer incidence rates are highest in central and Eastern Europe and lowest in

western Africa, but this partially suggests varying data quality worldwide. [17]

There is inverse relation between ovarian cancer risk and parity. Parous women are at significantly lower risk than nulliparous women. In our study, incidence of nulliparity was higher which is comparable with Misra et al., (16.00%) and Madan et al., (14.54%) [18-19]. the incidence of laterality was in concordance with Bhuvanesh et al., [8] (25.75%), while Madan et al., [18] and Verma et al., [20] reported a low incidence of 11% and 11.91% respectively. We found incidence of unilateral tumor comparatively higher than these studies. [21]

Conclusion:

Ovarian lesion possess wide gamut of histology. Specific diagnoses are made on routine gross and histological examination. Because of the geographic location, poverty and illiteracy, patients seek medical advice late in rural health facility. So, awareness among public and doctors, educating people, passive surveillance, and community screening facility will be helpful in early detection of the ovarian lesions and tumours.

References:

1. Prat J, D'Angelo E, Espinosa I. Ovarian carcinomas- at least five different diseases with distinct histological

- features and molecular genetics. *Human Pathol.* 2018;80;11-27.
2. Supriya BR, Patel R, Patel M. Histopathological evaluation of Non-Neoplastic and Neoplastic Lesions of Uterine Cervix at tertiary care centre. *Trop J Path Micro.* 2019;5(3)177-182.
 3. Scully RE, Young RH, Clement PB. Tumors of the ovary, maldeveloped gonads, fallopian tube, and broad ligament. *AmerRegPathol.* 1998.
 4. Sharma I, Sarma U, Dutta UC. Pathology of ovarian tumor- A hospital-based study. *Int J Med SciClin Invention.* 2014;1;284-286.
 5. Sikdar K, Kumar P, Roychowdhary NN. A study of ovarian malignancy: A review of 149 cases. *J ObstetGynaecol India.* 1981; 30:478-80.
 6. Modugno F. Ovarian cancer and polymorphisms in the androgen and progesterone receptor genes. *Am J Epidemiol.* 2004;159:319-35.
 7. Murthy NS, Shalini S, Suman G, Pruthvish S, Mathew A. Changing trends in incidence of ovarian cancer - the Indian scenario. *Asian Pac J Cancer Prev* 2009; 10:1025-30.
 8. Bhuvanesh U and Logambal A. Study of ovarian tumors. *J ObstetGynaecol India.* 1978;28: 271-77.
 9. Pilli GS, Suneeta KP, Dhaded AV, Yenni VV. Ovarian tumors: A study of 282 cases. *J Indian Med Assoc* 2002; 100:420, 423-24, 427.
 10. Gupta N, Bisht D, Agarwal AK, Sharma VK. Retrospective and prospective study of ovarian tumors and tumor-like lesions. *Indian J Pathol Microbiol* 2007; 50:525-7.
 11. Mankar DV, Jain GK. Histopathological profile of ovarian tumors: A twelve year institutional experience. *Muller J Med Sci Res* 2015;6:107-11.
 12. Ahmad Z, Kayani N, Hasan SH, Muzaffar S, Gill MS. Histological pattern of ovarian neoplasm. *J Pak Med Assoc* 2000;50:416-9.
 13. Pilli GS, Suneeta KP, Dhaded AV, Yenni VV. Ovarian tumors: A study of 282 cases. *J Indian Med Assoc* 2002; 100:420.
 14. Pradhan A, Sinha AK, Upreti D. Histopathological patterns of ovarian tumors at BPKIHS. *Health Renaissance* 2012;10:87.
 15. Kayastha S. Study of ovarian tumors in Nepal Medical College Teaching Hospital. *Nepal Med Coll J* 2009;11 :200.
 16. NIH Consensus Conference: Ovarian cancer. Screening, treatment, and follow-up: NIH Consensus Development Panel on Ovarian Cancer . *JAMA* 1995;273:491.
 17. Ferlay J, Soerjomataram I, Ervik M, et al. *GLOBOCAN 2012 v1.0: Cancer Incidence and Mortality Worldwide: IARC CancerBase No. 11.* Lyon, France: International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC), 2013. Online document at: <http://globocan.iarc.fr/Default.aspx>
 18. Madan A, Tyagi SP, Mohsin S. Incidence of ovarian tumors at Aligarh with particular reference to histopathological typing. *J ObstetGynecol India.* 1978;827-32.
 19. Risch HA, Marrett LD, Howe GR. Parity, contraception, infertility and the risk of epithelial ovarian. *Cancer.* 1994;140(7):585-97.
 20. Verma K, Bhatia A. Ovarian neoplasms- A study of 403 tumors. *J ObstetGynaecol India.* 1981;406-11.
 21. DIANE, S., Baldé, A. K. ., Camara, F. ., & Diane, M. H. . (2022). Problématique du traitement de limbo-conjonctivite et endémique des tropiques. *Journal of Medical Research and Health Sciences*, 5(9), 2244–2249. <https://doi.org/10.52845/JMRHS/2022-5-9-4>